

JOURNAL ON COMMUNICATIONS

ISSN:1000-436X

REGISTERED

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1 **Capacity Building of Primary Health Care Workers for Diagnosis and Counseling of Sickle**
2 **Cell Disease: A Protocol of Implementation Research**

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12 **Abstract**

13 Background and Objective

14
15 Sickle Cell Disease is a blood genetic disorder and a major problem among the tribal population
16 of India. There is no structured program in action in the country for the diagnosis, treatment, and
17 management of the disease. This study protocol aims to train health care workers i.e., Medical
18 officers, Auxiliary Nursing Midwifery , Laboratory Technician, and Community Health Officers
19 , for diagnosis and counseling for sickle cell disease through a training program in eight SCD-
20 endemic tribal districts of Rajasthan, India.

21
22 Methodology

23
24 The sub-districts of Udaipur, Banswara, Sirohi, Dungarpur, Pratapgarh, Pali, Chittorgarh, and
25 Rajsamand will be included in the study. The sub-districts having more than 50% tribal
26 population will be included in the study. The training sessions will be organized at the CHC/PHC
27 in eight districts. Data for this study will be collected from pre- and post-questionnaires given to
28 healthcare professionals during the training program. A counseling module in English and the
29 local language will be circulated to health worker to improve their knowledge regarding
30 diagnosis, management, and prevention strategies for sickle cell disease.

31
32 Discussion

33

34 The results of this study could provide information on the necessity of bolstering the capacity for
35 implementation research in endemic areas.

36

37 Expected outcomes

38

39 The outcomes of the study will provide a better understanding regarding the diagnosis, control,
40 and management of sickle cell disease among the health workers. The primary outcome will be
41 capacity building of the health workers in conducting screening of SCD and creating awareness
42 of sickle cell disease among tribes.

43 **Key words:** Implementation, Tribal, Counseling, Sickle cell anemia, capacity building

44

45 **Introduction**

46

47 Sickle cell disease (SCD) is an autosomal recessive blood disorder and a major problem among
48 the tribes living in hilly area of India¹⁻². SCD patients lack the required hemoglobin throughout
49 life; suffer severe pain, and organ damage that can result in premature death³. The prevalence of
50 SCD is anticipated to rise exponentially and it is predicted that 14,242,000 will be born with the
51 disease around the globe before 2050⁴. As a result of globalization, people will migrate more and
52 SCD will spread more over the world in the coming decades⁵. SCD has received little attention in
53 India's health and medical research as it has been considered a neglected health issue⁶⁻⁷. In India,
54 more than 44,000 births with SCD occurs yearly⁸. India is the second largest affected country in
55 the world by sickle cell disease⁹. The tribal population in India is spread transversely in 30 states
56 and union territories¹⁰⁻¹¹. Tribal residents of India are 8.6% of the total Indian population and in
57 the state of Rajasthan, they represent 13.6% of the total state population. Many studies were
58 conducted in the last 30 years to measure the problem and prevalence of SCA around the
59 country. The prevalence of the sickle cell trait and sickle cell disease in India was 8.33% and
60 0.41% among tribal population, respectively. Out of the 98 million tribal population of the
61 country, 11.3 million people have been screened for sickle cell disorder (Sickle Cell Disease
62 support corner Ministry of Tribal Affairs Government of India portal). We do not have a
63 structured SCD program in the country for the diagnosis and management of SCD. However, the
64 Government of India has initiated the National Sickle Cell Anemia Elimination Mission to
65 eliminate SCD by 2047. Therefore, screening of the population for SCD, treatment, and

66 counseling are required urgently to control the disease. There is no systematic approach in the
67 primary health care system existing in the country for the screening of the population for SCD.
68 The network of primary health centre is the only available resource to reach the community level
69 for preventive, promotive and curative services. Hence, a study is being implemented to develop
70 a structured program for the diagnosis and management of the SCD with a systematic approach.
71 Currently, sickle cell testing is available at limited tertiary level health facilities. Therefore, we
72 would like to expand the testing facilities at the Community health centre/Primary health
73 centre/Sub-Centre level of the tribal area. A basic definition of a health care worker is an
74 individual who provides direct medical care and services to the sick and injured, such as nurses
75 and doctors, or indirect medical waste handlers, laboratory assistants, and laboratory technicians,
76 are referred as a healthcare worker. In the present study Health Care Workers (HCWs) i.e.
77 Medical Officers (MO), Auxiliary Nursing Midwifery (ANM), and Laboratory technician (LT)
78 will be trained for the diagnosis of sickle cell disease. Community Health Officers will also be
79 trained for the genetic counseling. The effective execution of SCD prevention programs greatly
80 depends on counseling, community education, and awareness. Early diagnosis of SCD in
81 newborn babies allows earlier treatment. Counseling may improve early diagnosis of SCD
82 (antenatal and pre-natal check-ups); availability of treatment (availability of drugs and
83 experience man power); and enhance knowledge among the community to be aware about SCD.

84 The overall objective is to develop the capacity of the public health system for screening, treating
85 and counseling of SCD patient at the primary health care level.

86 **Methodology**

87 **Study area**

88 Eight districts selected for the study are situated in the southern part of the state of Rajasthan,
89 India. The ratio of the tribal population to the overall population as well as the density and size
90 of the tribal population were criteria considered while choosing the study area. These eight
91 districts (Udaipur, Banswara, Sirohi, Dungarpur, Pratapgarh, Pali, Chittorgarh, and Rajsamand)
92 were chosen because they have a higher proportion of the tribal population (Fig.1). All the sub-
93 districts of the eight districts were chosen based on the proportion of tribal population residing.

94 Only those sub-districts in each district were chosen where the proportion of tribal population
95 was greater than 50%.

96

97 **Figure 1. Eight districts to be screened for sickle cell diseases under the tribal sub-plan**
98 **region of Rajasthan, India.**

99 Study participants

100 About 2700 healthcare workers i.e., Medical officers, Auxiliary Nursing Midwifery (ANM),
101 Laboratory Technician (LT), and Community Health Officers (CHO) of selected study areas will
102 targeted for training for screening, treating and counseling.

103 Study design

104 The implementation study has cross-sectional and qualitative components and will be conducted
105 in a community as well as hospital settings. Data will be gathered for this hypothesis by the
106 qualitative study from the scores of the pre-and post-questionnaires were given to healthcare
107 professionals. One of the techniques available for assessing the effectiveness of an educational
108 training program is the pre-post survey. Its aim is to evaluate the impact of training health care
109 workers knowledge and skills to perform screening and management of SCD. The questionnaire
110 for HCWs was developed by brain storming with scientists working in SCD and previous
111 studies^{12, 13, 14, 15}. HCW and MaaBaadi (School) coordinators of the schools will be involved
112 through the government machinery system. The training will be divided into four parts: a) an

113 introductory part regarding sickle cell disease¹⁶: b) a demonstration for screening of sickle cell
114 disease ¹⁷ c) hands-on skill of solubility kit and point of care test ¹⁸⁻¹⁹ d) counseling for the SCD
115 participants. A question-and-answer session will also be there for solving the problem. Feedback
116 and suggestion from the training session and their search team will also be taken after the
117 training is finished at CHC/PHC level. The feedback and suggestions will be analyzed after each
118 training session. Health workers will do solubility tests in their respective MaaBaadi Centre and
119 hostel after being trained and upload their screened details on the National Sickle Cell Anemia
120 Elimination Mission Portal with the help of a mobile application created by the health ministry.

121 After training qualitative methods will be used to identify facilitators and barriers (of the
122 primary/community health care system) in accessing the SCD screening and management and
123 other similar program of the government health system with the help of closed-ended questions
124 for implementing screening programs.

125 **Screening& confirmatory test for sickle cell disease**

126 A solubility test will be used to detect the presence of sickle hemoglobin (HbS). This method is
127 primarily used for large-scale screening in a short time. HbS has decreased solubility in the
128 deoxygenated state in a hypotonic buffer which produces turbidity. 2mL whole blood sample will
129 be collected in EDTA containing vacutainer from sickle cell screen positive individuals for
130 confirmation of genetic status. The blood samples in a vacutainer will be transported to their
131 respective district hospital and stored at 4°C till analysis. Written informed consent of
132 individuals will also be taken in the local language for research and publication purpose. An
133 advanced laboratory will be established in each district for the analysis of hemoglobin. Cation
134 Exchange-High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) system will be installed in four
135 districts. Samples from the adjacent areas will be sent for analysis. Additionally, health
136 professionals will also be trained for conducting the confirmatory test by Cation Exchange-High
137 Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). High Performance Liquid Chromatography
138 (HPLC) of whole blood samples of positive cases and some negative cases will be carried
139 out using Bio-Rad Variant-II. The instruments will be calibrated with commercially available
140 controls, and samples will also be cross-checked for quality control from time to time. The
141 training will be given to the laboratory technicians of medical college or district hospitals as
142 described by Mohanty and Colah (2008)²⁰. After the confirmatory test, sickle cell trait and sickle

143 cell disease individuals will be counseling for further treatment. The SCD individual will be
144 referred to their respective PHC, CHC, and district hospital for treatment as per programme
145 guidelines²¹.

146 Counseling module will also be circulated to health workers to improve their knowledge of the
147 management and prevention strategies of sickle cell disease. Evaluation of the health
148 professional will be done just after the training and counseling part, by filling of a well-tested
149 post-questionnaire.

150 **Formative Research for existing health facility**

151 1. Assessment of knowledge and skills of HCWs.

152 2. Assessment of manpower and infrastructure required for screening and management of SCD.

153 **Implementation plan**

154 **Inclusive partnership approach**

155 During the initiation of the study, a meeting will be held with the TADD commissioner, CMHO,
156 and BCMO of respective health centers to finalize the agenda and schedules of the training. The
157 research team of the ICMR-NIIRCD, Jodhpur, will visit each of the districts and will train
158 medical officers, technicians, and paramedical staff for the solubility test. They will be trained to
159 diagnose the common symptoms of sickle cell disease and its management. They will be
160 informed about the intervention for the unhealthy person suffering from a sickle cell disorder.
161 Counseling training will be provided to the health professionals. The experienced researcher of
162 the team will train and assist in capacity building of the health care system, which further will
163 help in the implementation of the plan and will be reported in the final analysis. According to
164 guidelines received from NHM, ANM will do screening at their respective sub-center and
165 Community Health Officers will impart genetic counseling to them²².

166 The design and execution of the project will entail a broad representation of tribal communities
167 and staff from the health care, state government, and non-governmental organizations. This
168 training is mandatory for health care professionals by the office order, if anyone is absent on the
169 day of training second attempt or training will be given by video conferencing.

170

171 **Execution of strategies**

172 After the training sessions, ANM will do initial screening at the community level, Schools,
173 MaaBaadi, Aanganwadi centers, Hostel residents, etc. with the help of ASHA and MaaBaadi
174 teachers. Laboratory technician will do screening at the CHC/PHC level. All the individuals
175 found positive will be enrolled in the National Sickle Cell Anemia Elimination Mission and their
176 details will be uploaded by HCW on the National Portal of MoTA. Community health officer
177 will impart prevention and control strategies for sickle cell disease burden at the household,
178 community, school levels.

179 **Evaluation of the strategy:**

180 This study will be evaluated by the RE-AIM framework which is a guide to planning and
181 evaluation of programs according to the 5 key RE-AIM outcomes: Reach, Effectiveness,
182 Adoption, Implementation, and Maintenance²³.

183 **Reach:**

- 184 ● Target Population: the tribal populations residing in eight districts of the southern
185 part of Rajasthan with a high tribal population ratio.
- 186 ● Demographics: Newborn to 40 years.
- 187 ● Participation: Community settings, hospitals, and schools, ensuring a broad reach.

188 **Effectiveness:**

- 189 ● Outcome measurement: Knowledge, attitude, and practices of healthcare workers
190 before and after the training, intervention via pre- and post-questionnaires
191 followed by qualitative inquiry.
- 192 ● Disease detection: Using solubility tests and confirmatory tests like HPLC.

193 **Adoption:**

- 194 ● Engagement of Stakeholders: Adoption of the screening plan at different
195 organizational levels.
- 196 ● Training components: Solubility testing, counseling, referral

197 **Implementation:**

- 198 ● Training quality: Training and its feedback mechanism will provide insights into
199 the quality and effectiveness of the training.
- 200 ● Screening and Testing:
- 201 ● Role Delegation:
 - 202 - ANM for initial screenings,
 - 203 -Laboratory Technicians at CHC/PHC levels, and

204 -Community Health Officers for imparting prevention strategies

205 **Maintenance:**

- 206 ● Sustainability: The number of organizations and NGOs indicate involvement
- 207 ● Data Management: The uploading of details on the National Sickle Cell Anemia
- 208 Elimination Mission Portal (GoI)
- 209 ● Long-Term Strategy: By referring individuals with confirmed sickle cell disease
- 210 to respective health facilities for treatment and offering genetic counseling.
- 211

212

213 **Fig. 2 – Flow chart of the implementation research strategy**

214 **Data Management and Analysis**

215 Demographic and sickle status data of the individual will be entered at the National Health
 216 Mission portal (<https://sickle.nhm.gov.in/>). Credentials of this portal have been provided to the
 217 principal investigator by the National Health Mission. All the pre- and post-training assessment
 218 information will be collected from each healthcare worker by researcher and will be analyzed to
 219 assess the impact of training and capacity building activities.

220

221 **Expected outcomes**

222 The outputs of this study will help in better understanding of sickle cell disease; capacity
223 building of the health professionals in conducting screening tests and enhancing awareness in the
224 public and active involvement of society in the fight against Sickle Cell Disease. The
225 paramedical staff will screen the population of the tribal region in the future and also identify
226 barriers& challenges during screening.

227 **Discussion**

228 About diagnostic and prevention methods for sickle cell disease in the nation, this study will
229 provide a deeper understanding of sickle cell disease. Additionally, to help tribe's health in this
230 study, treatment for SCD will benefit from early diagnosis and an awareness campaign.
231 Counseling through primary healthcare system towards community level play a very significant
232 role in the successful implementation of SCD prevention programs. The results of this study
233 could document that makes a case for the necessity of bolstering capacity for implementation
234 research in the endemic areas in addition to providing insights into how sickle cell disease
235 healthcare initiatives could be implemented more effectively.

236 **Declaration of competing interest**

237 We declare no competing interests.

238 **Supplementary files**

239 All appendixes are given as supplementary data here:

240 1. Questionnaire

241 **Data availability**

242 No data is associated with this article.

243 **Funding**

244 This study has been funded by the Tribal Area Development Department, Udaipur, Government
245 of Rajasthan. (Grant No.F-1(M)/4(CTD)/Medical/sickle cell/ 2019-20/22865).India

246 **Ethics:** The Institutional Ethics Committee for Research on Human Subjects gave its approval to
247 the project (Approval number- D/05/SAC&SAG/2021-22/880 dated 12-12-2022). Teachers,
248 wardens, and guardians will give written informed consent for all the participants below 10 years
249 of age. Participants between the ages of 10-18 years will give their assent and consent will be
250 taken from the guardians. All the adults will give their consent before participating in the study.
251 The ethical concerns will be handled following the values outlined in the Helsinki principle.

252 **Acknowledgement:**

253 The authors are thankful to the Divisional Commissioner and Commissioner, Tribal Area
254 Development Department, Udaipur for providing support for the implementation of the study.
255 The authors are also grateful to Sh. Anurag Bhatanagar, Director, Swach for allowing to conduct
256 the study in the MaaBaadi Centers, and Hostels. We are also thankful to all the CMHO, BCMO,
257 and coordinators of the Maa Baadis, Schools and Hostels for their help in grouping the students
258 for conducting the study. We thank Sh. Rajneesh Kumar Mehan, Senior Technical Officers, Sh.
259 Trilok Kumar, Senior Laboratory Assistant, Sh. Kanhaiyalal Sharma, Sh. Pankaj sharma Medical
260 social worker, Raghunath Bisht, Laboratory Assistant, Rajkumar, MTS, and Projects staffs for
261 their extensive support during the training and screening work. The authors are also thankful to
262 Sk.Parveg Alam, Scientist-B to develop a map of the study sites.

263 **Credit authorship contribution statement:** SSM, MT, RKH, RKS, and AP conceived and
264 designed the study. SP, SSM, MT, and BVB wrote the protocol. All authors contributed to the
265 drafts before submission.

266 **Data Availability Statement:** No data associated with this manuscript.

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